

ECHO:

Expanding Concept and Methodology for Human Past Studies in the
Eastern Baltic Countries

Grant Agreement no 101159883

Deliverable 1.2 – Initial Data Management Plan

WP1 – Project Management

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Executive Summary

The Data Management Plan (DMP) outlines the principles and strategies for handling research data, metadata, and other materials that will be generated by the ECHO project. The DMP is composed under Work Package 1 (WP1) - Project Management.

The DMP ensures that all data generated, processed, stored and shared within the project adhere to the FAIR (Findable, Accessible, Interoperable, and Reusable) principles. This includes proper data documentation, secure storage solutions, controlled access, and compliance with the European Code of Conduct for Research Integrity (<https://allea.org/code-of-conduct/>), as well as ethical and legal standards and regulations on data protection.

The DMP is an is a living, dynamic document and will be revised and updated by the Project Coordinator annually.

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1. Data Summary

Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use it for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.

The published genomic datasets of ancient and modern individuals (e.g., <https://reich.hms.harvard.edu/allen-ancient-dna-resource-aadr-downloadable-genotypes-present-day-and-ancient-dna-data>; <https://reich.hms.harvard.edu/ancient-genome-diversity-project>; <https://evolbio.ut.ee/>) will be used in the analyses together with the newly generated data as context and to make comparisons with. Large datasets of present-day human genomes (1000 Genomes Project (1000 GP) Phase 3 (<https://doi.org/10.1038/nature15393>); Haplotype Reference Consortium (HRC) panel (<https://doi.org/10.1038/ng.3643>); 1000 Polish genomes (<https://doi.org/10.3390/ijms23094532>); Estonian BioBank (<https://doi.org/10.1101/2024.09.22.24313964>)) will also be used for genotype imputation in ancient human genomes.

What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?

The project will generate genomic data that will be produced using shotgun sequencing methodology on the Illumina NextSeq 2000 platform (<https://emea.illumina.com/systems/sequencing-platforms/nextseq-1000-2000.html>). The raw sequencing data will be stored in *fastq* format, the aligned data in *bam* format, genotype data in *PLINK* and *vcf* formats.

Contextual data of the bioarchaeological material will be collected to complement the genomic data. All the teeth and bone fragments will be photographed before destructive processing, and the photos will be stored in *jpg* format. The documented archaeological and osteological information (e.g., excavation time, descriptions of burials, radiocarbon dates, isotope data, estimates of biological sex and age at death based on morphological data) will be collected, stored as *pdf* files, Google documents and/or spreadsheets and linked with the genomic data using individual-specific sample IDs.

The project will re-use published genomic data in one of the available formats (*fastq/bam* for sequences and *plink/vcf* for genotypes). The project will re-use contextual data for published genomes in available formats (*xlsx/pdf*).

What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?

The data generation and re-use are central to the objectives of the ECHO project.

- The newly generated and published *genomic* data will be used within the Pilot Project to study demographic processes and signals of adaptation in the Eastern Baltics during the Iron Age period (aligns with the Objective to apply acquired knowledge to run the pilot as an interdisciplinary research of Eastern Baltic partners).

- Workshops' *educational materials* will contribute to enriching the methodological toolbox of the ECHO widening partners related to ancient genomic data analysis, bioinformatics and statistics, population demography inference and study of adaptations (aligns with the Objective of extending methodological expertise).
- Study visits and workshops' *protocols and guidelines* will be used to enhance international and interdisciplinary collaboration and to increase service provision capacity (aligns with the objective of developing communication between specialists of natural and humanities sciences and the Objective of ensuing mutually beneficial and long-term collaboration).

What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?

The total size of the sequencing data is expected to be up to 3 TB (<https://emea.illumina.com/systems/sequencing-platforms/nextseq-1000-2000/specifications.html>).

What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?

The bioarchaeological samples (teeth, bones) originate from the ECHO partner's collections (Prof. Rimantas Jankauskas (Vilnius University, Lithuania), Gunita Zariņa (Latvian University), Prof. Valter Lang (University of Tartu)).

We will extract DNA from bioarchaeological material of Iron Age individuals from Eastern Baltics. Sub-samples will be drilled, and DNA will be extracted manually in a dedicated ancient DNA clean room facility (<https://genomics.ut.ee/en/content/estonian-biocentre>). DNA will be purified, and dsDNA sequencing libraries will be prepared using an automated pipeline. The libraries will be screened using shotgun sequencing methodology on the Illumina NextSeq 2000 platform, producing around 20 million sequencing reads per sample. Samples with adequate endogenous DNA content will be sequenced to higher coverage to enable use in further analyses.

To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?

The genomic data generated during the project will be publicly available right after the research article is published for a future wide range of studies that involve human ancient genomes (genetic structure, migrations, social and kinship structure, adaptation processes etc). The new data represent a valuable resource that a) will fill in an existing gap in ancient genomic data from Iron Age Eastern Europe, including the Eastern Baltic region; b) will serve as a foundation for further collaborative projects between Baltic partners of the ECHO.

2. FAIR data

2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?

After publishing, the genomic data will be made available in a public repository, e.g. the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA;

<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/home>). Each study in the repository has a persistent and unique accession number, which will be reported in the journal publication, which itself has a Digital Object Identifier (DOI). Furthermore, each sample and each data file associated with a sample also have unique accession numbers in the repository.

Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery?

All newly generated ancient genomes will be accompanied by rich metadata.

What metadata will be created?

We create contextual data of the bioarchaeological material (see below) to complement genomic data.

What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.

Field-specific standards for reporting metadata in ancient DNA studies are currently being developed, e.g. MInAS: Minimum Information about any Ancient Sequence (<https://www.mixs-minas.org/#>). Members of the ECHO project actively contribute to this standardisation effort. We expect that the metadata standards will be released during 2025 and hence to apply these standards while documenting metadata within the ECHO project.

In the meantime, the list of metadata we reported in our previous research included contextual data of the bioarchaeological material to complement genomic data:

1. Geographical data:
 - geographic location (including multiple administrative levels to avoid confusion)
 - geographic coordinates
2. Archaeological data:
 - archaeological dating
 - radiocarbon dating (raw dates, QC values, isotope values, calibrated dates)
 - affiliation to archaeological culture (if available)
 - isotope data (if available)
3. Osteological data:
 - osteometric data (if available)
 - non-metric traits (if available)
 - paleopathologies (if available)
4. Visual data:
 - photos of pre-processed samples
5. Processing data:
 - sampled material (tooth/petrous bone/...)
 - sampling protocol (powder/chunk)
 - sample treatment (bleach yes/no)
 - DNA extraction protocol (high/low volume)
 - DNA extract treatment (inhibitor removal yes/no)
 - genomic library protocol (single stranded/double stranded)

- genomic library treatment (nonUDG/halfUDG/fullUDG)
- indexing (single/double)
- sequencing (Illumina NextSeq/HiSeq/NovaSeq)

The contextual information is linked with the genomic data of an individual through the unique ID used throughout the workflow.

Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimize the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?

Search keywords are usually provided as part of the journal publication and chosen to indicate the type of metadata of the study (e.g. archaeological period, cultural context). We anticipate that MInAS metadata documentation standards will incorporate keywords to metadata.

Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?

Currently, contextual data of the bioarchaeological material that complements genomic data is organised as part of Supplementary Material of a publication in the form of tables (xlsx) and text/schemes/photographs stored as one pdf document. It is easily findable, however, indexing of tabular data can be optimised. As stated above, standards for ancient DNA studies are in an active development phase, and we foresee that aspects such as data indexing will be incorporated soon so that the ECHO metadata collection and indexing by other researchers will be enabled.

What is important is that we plan to contribute the archaeological metadata that accompanies genomic data generated within this project to the BIAD: Big Interdisciplinary Archaeological Database (<https://biadwiki.org/>). BIAD is a relational database that aims to link various datatypes, allowing easy data retrieval and analysis.

2.2 Making data accessible

Repository:

Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?

The genomic data will be uploaded to a public repository, e.g. the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA; <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/home>). After publishing, the data will be made publicly available.

Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?

ENA is a standard trusted repository routinely used by academic researchers to deposit genomic data for public use. ENA repository ensures standard data format and genomic metadata information (standards for ancient genomic data are currently under development, see above) and its accessibility. ENA is free for anyone to use after registering; hence, no specific arrangements need to be made in this respect.

Does the repository ensure that the data is assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?

Each study in the ENA repository has a persistent and unique accession number which will be reported in a journal publication which itself has a Digital Object Identifier (DOI). Each sample and each data file associated with a sample also have unique accession numbers in the repository.

Data:

Will all data be made openly available?

After publishing, the genomic data will be made available in a public repository, e.g. the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA; <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/home>).

If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek the protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.

Genomic data will be made available right after publishing. An embargo system might need to be introduced so that only the original researchers or an approved group have access to the data before it becomes openly available to the wider research community. This allows the original researchers time to publish their findings and receive appropriate recognition for their work while still committing to the principles of open data in the long term.

Will the data be accessible through a free and standardized access protocol?

The genomic data in *bam* format will be available for download from ENA (<https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/home>) without any restriction.

If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?

There are no restrictions for use.

How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?

There is no need to ascertain the identity of the person accessing the data since there are no restrictions for access or use.

Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?

There is no need for a data access committee.

Metadata:

Will metadata be made openly available and licenced under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?

Metadata (contextual data of the bioarchaeological material that complements genomic data) will be published in the Materials and Methods, and Supplementary Materials sections of the journal publication. Newly generated genomic data can be accessed through a unique accession number that is assigned while uploading data to a repository and reported in the journal publication.

How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data is no longer available?

Sequencing data will be stored and be available indefinitely through public repositories designed to ensure the long-term preservation of digital data (e.g. the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA) <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/home>). Metadata will also be available indefinitely as part of a publication or, in future, as accompanying sequencing data uploaded to the repository indefinitely.

Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open-source code)?

The format in which the data will be deposited (*bam*) is generated and read with published standard software tools (Samtools, <http://www.htslib.org/>). This software is widely accepted by the international research community for data-sharing, analysis and storage of genomic data so there is no need to include code here.

2.3 Making data interoperable

What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices?

The data produced in the project are interoperable – the data formats that will be used are of common use in the field and the software that will be used are standard programs and openly available to everyone. The data can be combined with other datasets as is since the data processing methods used will be common in the field or reprocessed together with the other datasets to further minimise biases from data processing.

No official standard vocabularies are used in the field, but the software and formats used are common in the field, allowing for interoperability across data produced within the project.

In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow reusing, refining or extending them?

No official ontologies or vocabularies are commonly used in the field, but the software and data formats used in the project are widely used in the field, not

uncommon or project-specific, allowing for interoperability across data produced within the project.

Will your data include qualified references¹ to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?

Qualified references are not currently planned within the project.

2.4 Increase data re-use

How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?

The newly generated genomic data will be uploaded in standard format (*bam*) that is widely used in the field and will be available for re-use with published standard software tools (Samtools, <http://www.htslib.org/>). A publication will contain detailed information on data generation, processing and analyses accompanied by references to the software used.

Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard reuse licenses, in line with the obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?

The data will be made public under the Creative Commons CC BY 4.0 licence.

Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?

The data generated during the project will be made available immediately after the journal publication of the results.

Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?

The provenance of the genomic data generated within the ECHO project will be documented using appropriate standards (currently - as tabulated data that accompanies a publication; in the future we will implement MInAS standards (MInAS project (<https://www.mixs-minas.org/#>)) that will represent a part of the metadata that accompanies genomic data deposited in the public repositories).

Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.

Data quality assurance includes:

- Processing of bioarchaeological material is done in a dedicated clean facility of the Institute of Genomics (University of Tartu), following the guidelines of

¹ A qualified reference is a cross-reference that explains its intent. For example, *X is regulator of Y* is a much more qualified reference than *X is associated with Y*, or *X see also Y*. The goal therefore is to create as many meaningful links as possible between (meta)data resources to enrich the contextual knowledge about the data. (Source: <https://www.go-fair.org/fair-principles/i3-metadata-include-qualified-references-metadata/>)

working with highly degradable material to prevent data contamination.

- The laboratory workflow, including sample handling, sampling and decontamination, extraction (aDNA/proteins) and purification, including storage of the extract, genomic library preparation, genomic library amplification and purification, quality assessment and sequencing, are done following established protocols and can be found here (<https://www.protocols.io/view/ancient-dna-protocol-collection-university-of-tart-n92ldzbd8v5b/v1>).
- DNA from bioarchaeological samples undergo authentication procedures that include estimates of postmortem modification and contamination. These parameters are reported in the publication for each genomic sequence.
- Bioarchaeological sample tracking is performed via an in-house built database (*AirTable*). It is a SQL-based platform that allows the interconnecting of multiple data tables (project/collaborator, sample metadata, laboratory procedures/instruments/reagents, person in charge, associated publication, etc) to keep track of the samples.
- Data processing and analysis is done using established well documented software and algorithms. The newly introduced pipeline will be published in the publication where it was introduced.
- The project's results, including the data and the methods used to generate and analyse the data, will be subject to peer review as part of the scientific publication process. This provides an additional layer of quality assurance.

2.5 Other research outputs

The project will generate other data, including educational material (protocols and guidelines (in *pdf* format), pipelines and codes (e.g. in *R*, *python*, *bash* formats), reports and publications. The material will be stored in a dedicated project space in Microsoft SharePoint and will be made available via download from the project webpage (<https://echo-project.eu/>) during the period of the project and upon request after the project is completed. Published research articles will be available for an infinite time.

3. Allocation of resources

What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.) ?

There are no costs related to making the genomic data FAIR, thanks to the use of a free repository. However, open-access journal publications usually cost between 3,000 and 6,000 EUR per publication.

How will these be covered?

The publication costs will be covered either from the grant or from publication funds of the institute.

Who will be responsible for data management in your project?

During the project, the PI, Prof Kristiina Tambets, will be responsible for data management.

How will long term preservation be ensured?

The data deposited in the repository remains preserved there indefinitely without cost. Raw sequencing data, aligned data, genotype data as well, as final versions of analysis files will be stored long-term in a dedicated directory in the High-Performance Computing Cluster of the University of Tartu (UT HPC) under the management of the project PI Prof Kristiina Tambets.

4. Data security

What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?

Both during the project and long term, data will be stored in a dedicated directory in the UT HPC. The project stores are backed up: UT HPC Cluster file systems are backed up weekly; snapshot on a weekly basis. Only the project store owner (the researcher on the project) and users authorised by the owner have access to the project store.

Data is transferred over the secure education roaming network *eduroam*.

Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?

The genomic data will be safely stored for long term preservation in a public repository, e.g. the European Nucleotide Archive (ENA; <https://www.ebi.ac.uk/ena/browser/home>).

5. Ethics

Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing?

There are no ethical or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing.

Will informed consent for data sharing and long term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?

No personal data will be collected as part of the project.

6. Other issues

Do you, or will you, make use of other national/funder/sectorial/departmental procedures for data management?

No additional procedures will be used for data management

HISTORY OF CHANGES		
VERSION	PUBLICATION DATE	
1.0	31.03.2025	DMP initial version